

Trace analysis at the backdrop of women welfare : Assessment of heavy metals in vermilion

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Abstract : This study evaluated the content of heavy metals in samples of different varieties of vermilion (*Sindoor*) using ICP-OES. Use of vermilion is mandatory for large section of married Hindu women in India and the presence of probable heavy metals cadmium, chromium, mercury and lead in it have not been probed so far. The analyses were preceded by microwave assisted acid digestion. The results indicates that some maroon colored vermilion varieties contain maximum amount of heavy metals Hg (~82 ppm), Pb (30 ppm), Cr (6 ppm), while Cd < 1 ppm in most products. However, considering about 100 mg vermilion is applied everyday round the year by a married Indian Hindu women, the total amount of heavy metals applied to a individual annually becomes insignificant. For low cost vermilion annual amount of body application of Hg, Pb, Cr are only 3 mg, 0.3 mg, 0.01 mg. Hence the amount of heavy metals in vermilion is not level of concern.

Keywords : Vermillion, socio-religious custom, heavy metals, ICP-OES.

Introduction

Today's science is much more concerned than ever on the day-to-day life-style of human civilization keeping respect to diverse ethnic, regional and religious practices. This paper deals with a traditional practice of millions of women in the Indian sub-continent. The married women of Indian sub-continent and who belong to Hindu religion apply a colored powder, vermilion (locally known as *Sindoor*) as a symbol of auspiciousness on their forehead and also in the parting of hair (Fig. 1). According to census-data of India [2011]¹, ever married and currently married Hindu women population of all ages is 276 million (approx.). This constitutes about 23% of the total Indian population (1210.57 million). This huge population as a traditional practice use vermilion almost every day.

Therefore, this paper is a timely attempt to assess the heavy metal contents of vermilion. Such assessment is marker of exposure not effect, but might serve as an important document with regards to public health, general awareness and even to the legal issues.

The commercial vermilion may have different colors (red, maroon or orange) or may be available in different forms (powder or liquid). The amount, method and variety of vermilion used may vary depending on personal choice, region and socio-economic condition. There is no specified amount but almost 0.1 g of the powder form is required to cover up the region of application. Apart from the daily use, in some religious occasions higher amount is often applied. Repeated and prolonged use of vermilion requires quality check as the commercial varieties

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the experimental steps.

ies may contain various heavy metals. In ancient times, vermilion was prepared from natural ingredients like turmeric, alum etc.². However, with the emergence of a number of synthetic dyes, a variety of brilliant red and similar shades are now produced to make the product commercially viable. Some commercial grade may be adulterated with the colorful salts of lead, mercury, chromium and cadmium. For example, mixing of red lead (Pb_3O_4) would make the vermilion more attractive. Red color may also be derived from mercuric sulphide (HgS) commonly known as cinnabar. Cadmium sulfoselenide is another red to orange (depending on S/Se ratio) pigment used in the preparation of vermilion. The liquid vermilion remains on the applied area for a greater period of time rather than its powdered form. Often vermilion is applied on the hair parting without proper removal of the residual amount. So the applied amount remains in contact for several days leading to increased risks. As

these powders are directly applied to the skin, apart from allergic contact dermatitis, there is constant systemic intoxication. Some of the toxic elements and their compounds are water-soluble and sweat can promote the percutaneous absorption of the element³. In all these cases, depending upon the level and duration of exposure, the consumer is susceptible to a wide range of adverse biological effects⁴⁻⁶.

Various chemicals in consumer products have been documented to produce health hazards⁷⁻⁹. Heavy metals in particular are of great concern^{10,11}. Heavy metals like Hg, Pb and Cd penetrate skin through hair follicles and sweat ducts while Cr accumulate in the stratum corneum and may cause allergic contact dermatitis¹²⁻¹⁴. Although, the skin provides a protective barrier between external environment and internal organs, repetitive application of a particular product can lead to local effects. These include irritation, sensitization, allergy or photoreactions^{15,16}. Thus the products, which are applied on the human skin, should be monitored with utmost vigilance so far as toxicity is in question¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Lead and chromium are two potentially harmful metals that have aroused considerable concern. Lead impairs the renal, hematopoietic and nervous system and is related to deficiency in cognitive functioning²⁰. Lead poisoning is not only harmful to the women but also to the developing fetus producing congenital defects²¹. Amongst two oxidation states, Cr^{VI} is more toxic than Cr^{III} because the oxidizing potential of Cr^{VI} is high and can easily penetrate membranes²². It is enlisted as carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). Chromium(VI) is corrosive and allergic to the skin. Adverse effects of Cr^{VI} on the skin may include ulcerations, dermatitis and allergic skin reactions²³. Mercury is a neurotoxin. Prolonged use of products containing mercury can lead to inflammation of the liver, kidneys and urinary tract. Mercury compounds are readily absorbed through the skin on topical application and have the

tendency to accumulate in the body²⁰.

Several studies have been conducted on trace metal contents in skin care products and cosmetics²⁵⁻²⁷. However, to the best of our knowledge detailed study on the presence of heavy metals in vermilion has not been exploited. None of the samples, commercially available in the local market, have declared presence of heavy metals in their composition. The objective of the present study is to determine the content of potentially toxic heavy metals viz. cadmium, chromium, mercury and lead in varieties of vermilion samples available commercially and thereby assessment of exposure to the heavy metals by large fraction of Hindu married women living in the Indian sub-continent and abroad.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Sample collection : Different varieties of commercially available vermilion samples were collected from local market of Kolkata, India. These can be primarily classified according to (a) form – powder or liquid, (b) color – red, orange and maroon and (c) pricing – low and high end products.

De-ionized water (18.2 MΩ cm) was obtained from ThermoScientific Barnstead Nanopure water purification system. The chemical reagents 65% HNO₃ (suprapur) was procured from Merck, Germany and 70% HClO₄ GR was procured from Merck, India. SRMs used in ICP-OES analysis were procured from NIST, USA.

Sample preparation : Preceding sample measurement in ICP-OES, proper dissolution is required to

leach out metals from complex matrices²⁸. The process of determination of heavy metals in various samples of vermilion required matrix destruction, which was made possible via microwave digestion process. Microwave heating under specified temperature, pressure and time have been performed for a wide range of samples so that they were optimally ready prior to ICP-OES measurement. Accurately weighed powdered vermilion (0.1 g) was transferred to a TEFLON digestion tube, followed by the addition of 3 mL nitric acid (HNO₃) + 3 mL perchloric acid (HClO₄) mixture (1 : 1). The tube was sealed and acid digestion was carried out for 60 min using CEM MARS Xpress microwave digester. After sufficient cooling time, 8 mL of deionised water was added and digestion continued for another 30 min. Instrumental operating parameters for microwave digestion using CEM MARS Xpress is shown in Table 1. At the end of the digestion process, the digest was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min, filtered through Whatman 42 filter paper and was ready for measurements by ICP-OES. A reagent blank was simultaneously prepared along with the digested samples following every step except addition of vermilion.

Instrumentation :

ICP-OES, ICAP duo 6500 from Thermo-Scientific was used for measurement of heavy metals. Standard solutions (0.05 to 10 ppm) were prepared by appropriate dilution of ICP multi-elemental standard (MES) solution IX of 100 ppm strength with 2% suprapur HNO₃. A calibration curve was prepared with these standard solutions for all the heavy metals under investigation. Details of operating conditions

Table 1. Instrumental operating parameters for microwave digestion using CEM MARS Xpress

Amount of sample	Acid mixture	Volume used (mL)	Power (W)	Temp. (°C)	Rising time (min)	Holding time (min)
100 mg	HNO ₃ + HClO ₄	3 + 3	800	120	15	60
	Deionized water	8	800	120	15	30

and analytical characteristics of wavelengths, detection limits of specified heavy metals by ICP-OES are listed in Table 2. Schematic representation of the experimental procedure has been provided in Fig. 1.

Table 2. Details of operating conditions of ICP-OES and emission wavelength used for heavy metals measurement

Instrumental condition	Element	Emission wavelength (nm)
RF power : 1150 W	Cd	214.438
Pump rate : 50 rpm		228.802
Auxiliary gas flow : 1 L/min	Cr	267.716
Nebulizer gas flow : 0.6 L/min		359.349
Coolant gas flow : 12 L/min	Hg	184.950
	Pb	182.205
		216.999
		220.353

Results and discussion

Six brands and three colors of vermilion were analyzed for heavy metals lead, mercury, cadmium and chromium as shown in Table 3. Cd, Cr and Pb concentration were obtained taking the average value under the two (214.438 and 228.802 nm), three (267.716, 359.349 and 360.533 nm) and three (182.205, 216.999 and 220.353 nm) emission wavelengths respectively whereas Hg was determined from the single wavelength of 184.950 nm. For each wavelength the concentration obtained was the average of triplicate values. The results showed the presence of all these metals in variable amount.

It has been found that low-priced vermilion samples contain all the heavy metals more than 2 ppm except Cd. The low-priced maroon colored vermilion contains Hg as high as 82 ppm. In special religious festivals, idols of deity are submerged in water bodies. Usually during these cultural rituals, deities are smeared with high amount of vermilion (generally low cost ones) according to traditional practices. Therefore the amount of Hg present in orange/maroon vermilion may contaminate the water bodies, which eventually might be bio-magnified through human food chain.

Both medium and high priced products showed comparatively low content of Cd, Cr and Hg; though Pb content was found to be higher in maroon colored high priced vermilion (~ 30 ppm). The liquid forms of the vermilion – both red and maroon color contain lower amount of heavy metals.

Table 4 indicates the annual exposure of heavy metals applied to individual Indian women considering each individual applies daily 100 mg vermilion. The translation of Table 3 to Table 4 reveals the interesting fact that the total amount of heavy metal applied to any individual is indeed negligible. For example, low cost maroon colored vermilion contains as high as 82 ppm Hg, which is equivalent to only 3 mg Hg applied by single Indian women annually. The amounts of other heavy metals under question are negligible.

Table 3. ICP-OES data showing the amount of heavy metals in different varieties of vermilion samples

Sample	Pricing and form	Colour	Cd (ppm)	Cr (ppm)	Hg (ppm)	Pb (ppm)
1	Low-price, powder	Red	0.35±0.02	6.03±0.02	1.84±0.14	4.19±0.11
2		Orange	0.15±0.09	2.22±0.17	10.64±0.63	4.59±0.11
3		Maroon	0.14±0.002	6.17±0.36	81.86±3.85	7.86±0.39
4	Medium-price, powder	Red	0.01±0.001	1.57±0.02	6.26±1.76	5.08±0.07
5		High-price, powder	Red	0.04±0.001	1.15±0.57	1.64±0.34
6	Liquid form	Maroon	0.12±0.002	2.59±0.04	1.90±0.03	30.48±0.28
7		Red	0.13±0.005	1.62±0.13	0.34±0.02	2.91±0.23
8		Maroon	0.11±0.005	2.76±0.16	5.19±0.20	2.76±0.18

Table 4. Annual exposure to different heavy metals for married Indian women^a

Sample	Pricing and form	Colour	Cd (mg)	Cr (mg)	Hg (mg)	Pb (mg)
1	Low-price, powder	Red	0.01	0.22	0.07	0.15
2		Orange	0.01	0.08	0.39	0.17
3		Maroon	0.01	0.22	2.99	0.29
4	Medium-price, powder	Red	Negligible	0.06	0.23	0.18
5	High-price, powder	Red	Negligible	0.04	0.06	0.30
6		Maroon	Negligible	0.09	0.07	1.11
7	Liquid form	Red	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.11
8		Maroon	Negligible	0.10	0.19	0.10

^aConsidering 100 mg of vermilion is applied everyday.

Conclusions

The use of vermilion has a lot of social relevance as it is being deliberately applied to the body by millions of Hindu women from all strata of society every day over periods of many years. In order to prevent heavy metal adulteration in such type of cosmetic, analysis and gathering information about its composition is necessary. It is revealed from the present study, especially from Table 4, that the presence of heavy metals in vermilion, even for its low priced variety, is not at all level of concern. However, continuous legal vigilance is important for such product for the safety of millions of women.

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